

Improving soil quality and rice productivity with application of local decomposer microorganisms and liquid organic fertilizer in rainfed lowland rice at Gunungkidul regency, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Soil organic matter plays a role in improving rain fed rice productivity. The application of a combination of liquid organic fertilizer and decomposer microbes can reduce excessive inorganic fertilizer, and increase nutrient balances in soil. This research was conducted in rainfed lowland rice of Sidorejo village, Ponjong district, Gunungkidul in 2016 wet season to determine the effect of local decomposer microorganisms and liquid organic fertilizer on soil quality and rice yield. The eight treatments of manure and liquid organic fertilizers and three replicates were arranged in randomized completed block design. The results showed that application of LDM + liquid organic fertilizer increased dry grain yield of 10.76% compared with no LDM application. A single local decomposer microorganism can increase grain yield of 8.03% compared to without LDM application. The combination of LDM 2 (fruit waste) + LOF (rabbit urine + gamal leaf) + 60% inorganic fertilizer recommended dosage was not significantly different with the same treatment + 100% recommended dosage of chemical fertilizers. This means that combination of LDM 2 + LOF 2 could save chemical fertilizer 30%, and increased microbial population of 37.65% compared to control or treatment without LDM.

Keywords: *local microorganism, liquid organic fertilizer, soil quality, rice productivity*

INTRODUCTION

The management techniques of agricultural production are nowadays focused on a greater commitment to environmental sustainability. On this way, organic agriculture, as an alternative system to conventional agriculture, appears to be an environmentally friendly system and since mineral fertilizers abuse and misuse are responsible for health problems, environmental pollution

and water limited. The application both of organic and inorganic fertilizer in rainfed lowland rice should consider their dosage and nutrient balance in soil.

The application of inorganic fertilizers will absorb quickly by rice plants rather than organic fertilizers. However, excessive use of inorganic fertilizers for a long time will degrade soil quality such as the occurrence of land contamination by hazard compounds, as well as the soil structure will compact due to the continuous use of inorganic fertilizers (Aisyah et al., 2006). Compared with conventional organic fertilizer, the abundant organic matter and soluble nutrients in the liquid organic fertilizers could maintain soil sustainability and plant health. In addition, the integration of water and fertilization patterns could improve the nutrient use efficiency and decrease the risk of nutrient loss. Moreover, the special compounds in liquid organic fertilizers, such as chitin, humic and fulvic acids, and other biopolymers, can be biostimulants to plants. The fertilizer application according to the needs of plants or specific location will improve soil degradation due to excessive use of inorganic fertilizers. The excessive application of fertilizers will be in inefficient fertilization, and vice versa if the use of fertilizers with dosages more lower than the needs of plants will cause rice production will not optimum as a result of nutrient imbalances in the soil. Therefore, it is necessary to take steps that can make efficient use of inorganic fertilizers by combining organic fertilizer and the addition of biological fertilizers. Suriadikarta et al. (2010), stated that application liquid fertilizer and biological fertilizer, which containing microorganisms from local environment were often known as LMO (local microorganisms) can improve soil fertility. Furthermore, Suhastyo et al. (2013) stated that local microorganism is useful in providing nutrients for the growth and development of rice plants. Local microorganisms can also streamline the administration of inorganic fertilizers, so that inorganic fertilizer can be reduced. The use of microorganisms derived from local ingredients is not yet widely known, and there is not much research on inorganic fertilizers combined with local decomposer microorganisms.

The rehabilitation of agricultural land by applying organic fertilizer is expected to increase soil organic matter content more than 2%. The role of organic matter is very important because organic matter is the heart of soil physical, chemical and biological processes that plays a major role in supporting plant growth. Application of organic matter which decomposed completely (C / N ratio of 12) can provide nutrients that are more easily absorbed into the soil. In relation to improving land quality and rice productivity, application of organic liquid fertilizer is one alternative technology that can be easily practices by small holder farmer.

The liquid organic fertilizer is a solution of decomposition of organic materials derived from crop residues and animal waste which contains more than one element. The advantage of liquid organic fertilizer is that it can quickly overcome nutrient deficiencies and is not a problem in nutrient leaching and does not damage crops that are cultivated even if used as often as possible. Besides this fertilizer has a binding material so that the fertilizer solution given to the soil surface can be directly used by plants.

The objectives of this study were to determine the effect of local decomposer microorganisms and liquid organic fertilizer on the growth and rice yield of Inpari 19 variety in rainfed lowland rice at Ponjong District, Gunungkidul Regency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted in rainfed lowland areas owned by cooperators farmers in Sidorejo village, Ponjong district, Gunungkidul regency with a rather flat topography of 3-10%. The average annual rainfall in Ponjong district was 2129 mm with irrigation relying on rainwater plus supplementer water sources from deep bore well. The soil pH in the study area was classified as slightly alkaline (pH 7.32-7.67), while the C-organic content and N-total were 1.21% and 0.13%, then the C / N ratio was 11.18 (all included in the low category). The type of soil is classified as Inceptisol. The study was conducted during second Planting Season (February - May 2017).

The tools that used in this experiment were tractors, diesel pumps, long hoses, hoes, 2: 1 jarak legowo spacing, sprayers, measuring cups, meters tool, stationery, cameras, labels, thermometers, analytical scales, biomass scales, sacks, buckets, plastics, hoes, sickles and other rice cultivation tools commonly used by farmers.

The materials used in this experiment includes were rice seed of Inpari 19 with a blue label, banana bulb as the local decomposer microorganism, fruit waste, sugarcane waste liquids, coconut water, rice washing water, cleresidae leaves, gamal leaves, cow urine, rabbit urine, Urea, SP-36, KCl and Phonska, and some chemical pesticides.

The experimental method used randomized completely block design (RCBD) and replicated 3 times, where the farmer's land as repeated. The treatments tested in this experiment consisted of

- I. Farmer treatment (control),
- II. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha without local decomposer microorganism (LDM) + 100% recommended dosage of inorganic fertilizer,
- III. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 (banana weevil),

- IV. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 (fruit waste),
- V. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 + liquid organic fertilizer (LOF) 1 (cow urine + extract of *Clotalaria* sp leaf),
- VI. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 + LOF 2 (rabbit urine + extract of *Gliricidia* sp leaf),
- VII. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 + LOF 1 + 60% dosage of recommended fertilizer,
- VIII. Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 + LOF2 (rabbit urine + extract of *Gliricidia* sp leaf) + 60% dosage of recommended fertilizer. The size of the experimental plot follows the farmer's ownership land (on farm research).

Planting was done when rice is young (about 16-18 days after spreading rice seeds). The 2 seedlings was transplanted each planting hole. Embroidering is done when the plants are 7 days after planting. The fertilization was carried out 3 times, where Ponska and SP-36 as basal fertilizers were applied at planting time. The second application with using Urea and KCl was done at 14 DAT and third fertilization when the plants were aged 35 with doses according to treatment.

Local decomposer microorganism spraying was carried out according to treatment. The type of local decomposer microorganism (LDM) used was banana weevil LDM and fruit waste LDM. While the source types of liquid organic fertilizers were cow urine + extract of *Clotalaria* sp leaf and rabbit urine + extract of *Gliricidia* sp leaf. The LDM was applied at 15 days after planting (DAP), 25 DAP, 35 DAP and 45 DAP. The pests and diseases were controlled by spraying pesticides. Spraying of chemical pesticide was carried out if an attack of certain pests or infections has been identified.

Supporting observations consisted of soil analysis, level of pest and disease attack, and agroclimate conditions of the study site. While the main observation consisted of plant height, number of tillers, number of productive tillers, number of filled grain per panicle, number of filled grains per clump, Tassel Length, weight of filled grain per clump, weight of 1000 grains, weight of dried harvesting, weight of dry milled rice, total microbes population, and Some chemical soil properties before application and after harvesting.

The data obtained were analyzed statistically using anova test at 5% level to find out whether or not there were significant differences between treatments. If there is a real difference between or part of the treatment, Duncan's multiple distance test at 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.05$) will done.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agroclimate conditions during the study

The averaged maximum and minimum temperature during the experiment was 33.5°C and 24°C. As usual the temperature greatly affects the growth of rice plants and grain filling. The low temperatures and high humidity at flowering stage can affect the fertilization process so that the grain becomes empty. Actually every 1°C increase in temperature will reduce the yield by 0.6 tons / ha (Harington, 2010).

The temperature is very related to humidity, the averaged humidity during the experiment is 60%. Soil moisture affects the growth of rice plants either directly or indirectly. If the humid conditions around the rice plantations will cause the appearance of disease attacks and the resistance of rice plants will be reduced (Makarim and Suhartatik, 2009).

During this experiment the watering of rice field is carried out relying on rain water (second planting season) and if the rainfall has begun to decrease then additional irrigation was taken from the deep wells near the rice field area. Watering is carried out with a dry wet irrigation system (intermittent irrigation) with an interval of 4 days, which was irrigated for 2 days by depth pump well up to 5-7 cm then dried for 4 days every weeks up to flowering stage of rice plant growth.

Rice plant growth and yield components

Table 1 presents that total panicle during 45 DAP (maximum vegetative stage) for combination of both local decomposer microorganism and liquid organic fertilizer were more higher significantly the amount of total panicle compare to control and single organic fertilizer ($p < 0.05$). This condition was similar with the research of Canfora *et al.* (2015), which reported that liquid organic fertilizers containing stillage and vermicompost promoted the root growth of rice plant and improved the soil microbial communities *Eubacterial* and *Archaeal* diversity and increase the diversity of the soil's microbial community, as well as the related enzyme activities and nutrient cycles. Then this environmental condition can be promoted to the yield component of rice plant.

Table 1 The plant height and total panicle during planting season of rice Inpari 19 variety

Treatment code	Plant height 21 DAP (cm)	Plant height 45 DAP (cm)	Total panicles at 21 DAP	Total panicles at 45 DAP
I	44,82 b	104,97 b	6,97 bc	9,97 b
II	42,67 b	109,43 ab	6,77 c	9,83 b
III	47,93 a	106,18 a	7,63 b	10,76 b
IV	47,19 a	110,83 ab	7,92 ab	13,87 a
V	48,12 a	108,17 a	8,75 a	12,34 ab
VI	46,24 ab	101,42 a	8,41 a	13,52 a
VII	48,39 a	105,51 ab	8,89 a	13,24 a
VIII	47,18 a	109,33 a	8,94 a	13,93 a

Notes : The number which followed by the same notification it was not significant treatment based on Duncan Multiple Range Test on $f=5\%$

The Chemical fertilizer offers nutrients which are readily soluble in soil solution and thereby instantly available to plants. While nutrient availability from organic sources is due to microbial action and improved physical condition of soil (Sarker et al. 2004). The increase in plant height, number of tillers per hill, spikelet number per panicle, in response to application of organic and chemical fertilizers is probably due to enhanced availability of nutrients. The variation in plant height due to nutrient sources was considered to be due to variation in the availability of major nutrients. Masluki et al. (2016) observed that the available nutrients in the rice field might have helped in enhancing leaf area, which thereby resulted in higher photo-assimilates and more dry matter accumulation. These results are supported by the findings of Swarup and Yaduvanshi (2000) and Yadana et al. (2009).

The effect of some local decomposer microorganism (LDM) and liquid organic fertilizer (LOF) on the yield component of Inpari 19 rice variety was shown in Table 2. From this result it was observed that the number of total filled grain as well as total tiller per clump rice were more higher by application both combine local decomposer microorganism and liquid organic fertilizer compare to the farmer treatment (control) even to the single application of organic fertilizer (only apply LDM or LOF) and given very significant effect between its treatment.

It was similar to the research that conducted by Morteza et al. (2011), which reported that the grain yield and its components were significantly increased in the all treatments (apply by organic fertilizer) over control. An increase in the grain yield at the above mentioned treatments was may be due to the increase of 1000-grains weight, panicle number, number of fertile tiller, flag leaf length, number of spikelet, panicle length per rice plant.

Table 2. The effect of some Local Decomposer Microorganism (LDM) and Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) on the yield component of Inpari 19 rice variety at Ponjong – Gunungkidul

Treatment code	Length of tiller (cm)	Total of tiller per clump	Total of filled grain per tiller	Weight of 1000 grain (gr)
I	24,85 b	9,43 c	98,40 d	24,27 b
II	24,01 b	9,27 c	98,28 d	24,16 b
III	25,57 ab	10,51 b	108,87 c	25,06 a
IV	26,55 a	11,95 b	116,03 b	25,14 a
V	27,03 a	12,13 a	119,05 ab	25,28 a
VI	27,52 a	12,69 a	121,42 a	25,34 a
VII	27,11 a	11,94 ab	117,66 b	25,17 a
VIII	27,78 a	12,74 a	121,37 a	25,39 a

Notes : The number which followed by the same notification it was not significant treatment based on Duncan Multiple Range Test on $\alpha=5\%$

The effect of some local microorganism (LMO) and liquid organic fertilizer (LOF) on the yield and biomass of Inpari 19 rice variety was presented on Table Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + local decomposer microorganism 2 (fruits waste) + liquid organic fertilizer 2 (rabbit urine + extract of Gliricidi leaf) + 60% recommended inorganic fertilizer the highest dry weight milled grain and it was not significance different to the treatment given by apply the livestock manure 5 tons /ha + local microbes from fruits waste (LDM 2) + liquid organic fertilizer 2 (rabbit urine + extract of Gliricidi leaf) + 100% recommended inorganic. It means for fertilizing rain fed rice crop at Ponjong district, Gunungkidul can save 40% the amount of total inorganic fertilizer and even the quality of grain yield of rice become more better compare to the farmer treatment and moreover the soil microbes can be more active because of its favorable environment.

Table 3. The effect of some Local Microorganism (LOM) and Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) on the Yield and Weight of Biomass Inpari 19 rice variety at Ponjong district – Gunungkidul regency

Treatment code	Weight of Biomass (ton. ha ⁻¹)	Weight of harvested Grain (ton. ha ⁻¹)	Weight of rice straw (ton. ha ⁻¹)	Dry Weight of milled grain (ton. ha ⁻¹)
I	16,17 c	6,67 c	9,50 c	5,70 c
II	17,05 b	6,24 c	10,81 b	5,43 c
III	16,52 bc	7,49 b	9,03 c	6,22 bc
IV	17,59 a	7,68 b	9,91 bc	6,32 b
V	17,42 a	7,55 b	9,87 bc	6,37 b
VI	17,76	8,02 ab	9,74 bc	6,71 a
VII	17,12	7,83 b	9,29 bc	5,96 c
VIII	17,95	8,34 a	10,61 a	6,78 a

Notes : The number which followed by the same notification it was not significant treatment based on Duncan Multiple Range Test on $\alpha=5\%$

A single LDM application increases dry grain yield of 8.03% compared with no LDM application. The combination of LDM 2 (fruit waste) + LOF (rabbit urine + gamal leaf) + 60% inorganic fertilizer recommended dosage given results is not significantly different from the same treatment + 100% recommended dosage of chemical fertilizers, which it means that the LDM 2 + LOF 2 combination application is able to save chemical fertilizer about 40%, besides improve soil physical, chemical and biological properties where the growth of microbial population has increased 37.65% compared to control or treatment without LDM (Table 5).

The rice field properties by application of Local Microorganism and Liquid Organic Fertilizer

The results of the initial soil analysis are presented in Table 4. Soil organic carbon and total nitrogen contents were 1.20 % and 0.17 %, respectively. The phosphorus and potassium extractable HCl 25% were > 100 mg/kg and were > 20 mg/kg soil, respectively. Samples of the soil were analyzed to determine the initial microbial biomass population levels and it was recorded as much as 4.12×10^7 CFU /g soil.

Table 4. The chemical soil properties before treatment and after harvesting rice as the affect of application some Local Microorganism (LOM) and Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) on rainfed lowland rice at Ponjong district – Gunungkidul regency Chemical soil properties before rice planting

Number sample	Soil depth (cm)	pH H ₂ O	Soil Texture (%)			C-org (%)	N-tot. (%)	P ₂ O ₅ mg / 100 g soil	K ₂ O	CEC me/100g
			sand	dust	clay					
1	0-20	7,36	18	23	60	1,19	0,13	184	24	41,84
2	0-20	7,65	14	21	65	1,18	0,10	161	21	38,57
3	0-20	7,32	17	22	61	1,24	0,12	178	26	43,82
Means	0-20	7,44	16	22	62	1,20	0,17	174	23,6	41.41

Table 4b. The chemical soil properties after harvesting as affect application of Local Micro Organism and Liquid Fertilizer on Ponjong - Gunungkidul

Treatment code	pH H ₂ O	C-org (%)	N-tot. (%)	C/N rasio	P ₂ O ₅ mg / 100 gr soil	K ₂ O	CEC me/ 100g
II	7,17	1,17	0,15	7,80	168	25	41,57
III	7,22	1,49	0,18	8,27	175	31	45,82
IV	7,06	1,87	0,19	9,84	192	38	44,71
V	7,10	1,62	0,20	8,15	185	29	46,46
VI	7,20	1,98	0,23	8,61	198	37	49,32
VII	7,06	1,78	0,19	9,36	187	34	44,87
VIII	7,15	1,93	0,21	9,19	195	39	48,26

After harvesting soil samples were analyzed and its were shown in Table 4b, which indicated that application of local decomposer microorganism with completed soil nutrients e.q. fermented waste fruits have effected on increased C organic soil (treatment IV,V,VI,VII,VIII) than limited source of soil nutrient (treatment I, II and III)

The combination of both of local microorganism and liquid organic fertilizer increase C organic, P total and K total and have significant different compare to the single organic fertilizer application and control (farmer practices).

Table 5 The total microbes during generative stage of Inpari 19 rice Variety on 76 DAP

Treatment Code	Treatment	Total mikrobos population (CFU /gr soil)
I	Farmer Treatment (control)	3,68 x 10 ⁷
II	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha without Local decomposer microorganism (LDM)	7,42 x 10 ⁷
III	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 (banana weevil)	5,34 x 10 ⁸
IV	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 (fruits waste)	6,51 x 10 ⁸
V	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 + Liquid Organic Fertilizer 1 (cow urine + extract of clotalaria leaf) + 100% anorganic recommendation	8,62 x 10 ⁸
VI	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 + Liquid Organic Fertilizer 2 (rabbit urine + extract of gliricidileaf) + 100% anorganic recommendation	1,27 x 10 ⁹
VII	Application of livestock manure 5 tons / ha + LDM 1 + LOF 1 + 60% anorganic recommendation	5,34 x 10 ⁸
VIII	Application of livestock manue 5 tons / ha + LDM 2 + LOF 2 + 60% anorganic recommendation	1,36 x 10 ⁹

Table 5 indicates that microbial population increased after applying organic fertilizer, either from local decomposer microorganism or leaf organic fertilizer. While the total microbes population before it was conducted th study was only 4.12 x 10⁷ CFU /g soil with three time replications. However, it showed that the soil condition in the rainfed lowland rice was suitable and promoted the development of more higher microbes population and stimulated more nutrients uptake for rice root and affected to the increasing signifcantly rice yield compared to the initial value observed.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The averaged dry grain yield with applying LOM + liquid organic fertilizer increased as much as 10.76% compared with no LOM application. Whereas with a single local decomposer microorganism also increased dry grain yield of 8.03% compared to without an LOM application.
2. The fertilizer application of combination LOM 2 (fruit waste) + LOF (rabbit urine + extract of Glirisidia sp leaf) + 60% inorganic fertilizer recommended dosage was not significantly different from the same treatment + 100% recommended dosage of anorganic inorganic recommendation fertilizers, its means the both of combine LOM 2 + LOF 2 application can save 40% of chemical fertilizer.
3. Application of both local decomposer microorganism and liquid organic fertilizer into Inceptisols in rainfed lowland rice at Ponjong district,

Gunungkidul can improve soil physical, chemical, biological properties which the growth of microbial population has increased 37.65% compared to control and treatment without application of local microorganism (LOM)

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